

TOPIC DIRECTIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract. *This article deals with the development of entrepreneurship, the development of small business and small entrepreneurship, consolidation of the national economy, and rapid economic growth.*

Keywords: *small business, development, growth, income, strategy, entity.*

INTRODUCTION. Currently, special attention is paid to the development of small business and entrepreneurship in our country. Because the development of small business and small entrepreneurship is a strategic task of the economic development of our country. Today, this area takes a leading position not only in accelerating the growth of the economy, but also in solving the problems of increasing employment and income of the population, which are extremely important for our country.

In the conditions of deepening of the environment, the development of economic, financial and personnel strategies, as well as strong organizational and management structures, is of great importance to ensure the competitive advantages of any enterprise. "The fact that the role and position of small business and corporate entrepreneurship is becoming more and more strengthened is evidence of the positive changes taking place in the structure of our economy. It envisages raising the development of small business and commercial entrepreneurship in our country to new heights.

In 1991, the first legal normative document on the development of small business and entrepreneurial entities in the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted, the Law "On Entrepreneurship". In accordance with this law, the protection of activities, legal obligations, responsibilities and interests of small business and entrepreneurial units is guaranteed by the state. In fact, on December 21, 1995, the law "On encouraging the development of small business and foreign entrepreneurship" adopted by the Supreme Assembly of the Republic of Uzbekistan provided even more benefits to businessmen engaged in small business. This, in turn, will further activate the work of businessmen engaged in small business, increase the size of the country's gross national product, slow down inflationary processes, created a wide opportunity to stabilize and develop the economy. In order to implement the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 7, 2014 "On additional measures to further improve the investment climate and business environment in the Republic of Uzbekistan", to increase the protection of the rights and interests of entrepreneurs, to limit the scope of inspections of their financial and economic activities, to provide additional tax benefits and advantages, mechanisms for the implementation of external economic activity to codify entrepreneurship regulatory legal documents aimed at liberalizing the activities and increasing the accuracy of the activities of state bodies were adopted. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legal Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at further strengthening the reliable protection of real property and business units and

eliminating obstacles to their rapid development" served as an important document in the implementation of this document. According to this law, changes and additions were made to more than 40 legal documents related to almost all aspects of the activity of business entities. The current task of the economic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan is defined by the development of small business and small business, giving it wide economic freedom.

"Increasing the competitiveness of the national economy by deepening structural changes, modernizing and diversifying the leading sectors of the national economy, ensuring the balance and stability of the national economy, increasing the share of tourism, service provision, small business and commercial entrepreneurship in its structure.

In this regard, special attention is paid to the development of small businesses and entrepreneurship in our republic. Because the development of small business and small entrepreneurship is considered as a strategic task of the economic development of our country.

The current stage of our country's development is characterized by the consolidation of the national economy and rapid economic growth. Our government, personally the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I. Karimov, has done a lot to raise the reputation of our country on the international level, open a wide path to foreign investments, and support foreign entrepreneurship.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. The purpose of studying these areas of economics is to regulate the national economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to define economic policies, and to create factors for the protection of national economic interests on an international scale. Small business and entrepreneurship studies the behavior of individual economic units. It includes consumers, workers, landowners, investors, farmers, productions, enterprises, and any individual that plays an important role in the functioning of the economy, that is, a social entity or an economic unit. Its focus is on the relative price of goods, individual markets, and the distribution of specific resources to achieve the goal. Small business and entrepreneurship, for example: why customers agree to buy these goods, including the price of the goods and their profit margin,

Our efforts to improve the business environment in our country are positively reflected in the ratings of international economic organizations. In October of last year, the World Bank announced the "Business" rating. In this ranking, Uzbekistan rose 16 places in just one year and took the 87th place.

It should be noted that our country currently ranks 42nd in the world according to the so-called "support for new business", 32nd in terms of ensuring the execution of concluded contracts, and 75th in terms of the friendliness of the bankruptcy system, which is applied favorably to economically insolvent enterprises. According to the indicator called "Lending to small business entities", Uzbekistan has risen from 154th place to 42nd place in the last three years and improved its rating by 63 positions last year.

In the speech of the World Bank, it was noted that Uzbekistan is among the ten countries in the world that have achieved the best results in terms of improving the business environment for entrepreneurship in recent years. I would like to emphasize that as a result of the reforms in this direction, the share of small business and commercial entrepreneurship in our gross domestic product has increased from 31 percent in 2010 to 53.3 percent today, or has increased 1.7 times. At the moment, the share of small business and foreign entrepreneurship in the economic sectors

in this area is 27.0 percent in export (26.0 percent in January-December 2022), 39.6 percent in commerce (45.3 percent), and 58.4 percent in services. percent (61.4 percent), in construction - 65.1 percent (66.9 percent) and in employment -78.3 percent (78.2 percent).

**Figure 1. The share of small business and foreign entrepreneurship
(as a percentage of the total volume)**

This area takes a leading position in solving the problems not only of accelerating the growth of the national economy, but also of providing employment to the unemployed population and raising the standard of living.

But at the same time, there are some problems in this regard.

It is believed that the reason for this is that people who are starting small business and military entrepreneurship have a lot of confusion about what to start, how to organize it, and how to manage it.

One of the important factors of economic development in the conditions of market relations is the development of small business and small business activities.

This is determined by changes in market conditions or by the influence of internal and external factors of the enterprise. However, the main goal of an entrepreneur is not only to see interest (profit), but also to carry out activities that ensure profitable operation in the market. For this purpose, it is necessary to create a mechanism adapted to the management of entrepreneurship and modern management tools that support it, and to ensure its effective use. In market conditions, he always takes into account the supply and demand in the market and uses his powers to manage the business;

- an entrepreneur looks for ways to reduce production costs by taking actions that ensure camaraderie;
- individuals who respond to the business's provard results, create sufficient opportunities to conduct their business in free terms and conditions;
- the final results of a small enterprise, i.e. its profit or loss, will be known only in the process of buying and selling in the market;
- A small business entrepreneur does not know for sure what the risk will be in the market or what the final result will be.

Thus, entrepreneurship is a special type of economic activity, based on independent initiative, responsibility, profit-oriented, goal-oriented activity.

Entrepreneurship is a special type of economic activity, the initial level of which is usually evaluated by the activity of thinking or its result, only then it takes a material form.

Entrepreneurship is defined as the presence of creativity in the process of innovating, changing the production of goods or organizing an enterprise (including a small enterprise).

Creative aspects of entrepreneurial activity are expressed in the implementation of new methods or new technologies of production organization in a new system of management.

In the interaction between entrepreneurship and the consumer, entrepreneurship belongs to the category of active entity. The consumer plays an active role. It acts as an indicator of the consumer business process in the analysis of mutual relations. It is possible to realize all the things that make up the subject of the entrepreneur's activity. From this, the consumer evaluates the product and then buys this or that product readiness is determined. An entrepreneur should take into account the consumer's mood, interest, and interests in planning and organizing his activities.

We can consider the books and manuals of the most popular economists today, which analyze the science of small business and entrepreneurship. Economy is production, distribution, consumption of goods and services, as well as provision of material resources. For this purpose, we tried to use foreign theoretician and experimenter in our own, using a number of foreign literature.

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